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Microbial Contribution to Soiling and Its Impact on Photovoltaic Module Soiling in Arid Zones of the Atacama Desert

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ABSTRACT

Soiling is one of the main challenges that affect the long-term performance of photovoltaic systems, especially in hyper-arid environments. Although the impact of mineral dust and atmospheric aerosols is well understood, the contribution of microbial communities to soiling accumulation and optical losses is not. This study investigates the biological mechanisms underlying the formation of biofilms on photovoltaic glass surfaces in the Atacama desert, one of the most irradiated regions. Using a combination of microbiological, metagenomic, morphological and chromatographic analyses, we demonstrate that bacterial strains isolated from the genera *Arthrobacter*, *Dietzia*, and *Kocuria* within soiling layers exhibit remarkable tolerance to high UV radiation and desiccation. Biofilm-forming taxa are identified, including *Bacillus*, *Sporosarcina*, *Bhargavaea*, *Mesobacillus*, *Cytobacillus*, *Planococcus*, *Peribacillus*, and *Kocuria*. *Dietzia maris* and *D. kunjamensis* subsp. *schimae*, are found to synthesize photoprotective carotenoids, with spectral features consistent with lutein-like compounds or related xanthophylls, which may interfere with photovoltaic performance optically. Field emission scanning electron microscopy imaging confirmed the formation of extracellular polymeric matrices capable of encapsulating cells and mineral particles, thereby enhancing surface adhesion and reducing the efficiency of cleaning processes. Current–voltage curve measurements revealed short-circuit current losses of up to 30.66% in colonized samples, highlighting the significant impact of microbial biofilms on energy output. These findings emphasize the importance of incorporating biological variables into soiling models and mitigation strategies, especially in regions with high solar potential.

1 | Introduction

Photovoltaic (PV) solar energy has emerged as a leading technology driving the global energy transition. The sustained reduction in the cost of materials, equipment and supplies has fueled this rapid growth, enabling large-scale deployment over the past

decade [1]. Examples of this expansion include the accelerated development of solar power plants in regions with high solar irradiance, such as North Africa, the Middle East, southwestern USA, India and Australia, where climatic conditions allow the efficient utilization of solar resources [1, 2]. However, this growth also faces significant operational challenges, one of which is

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soiling. Recent estimates suggest that soiling can result in average annual energy production losses of over 3%, with values in severely affected regions reaching above 20%, resulting in a global economic impact of billions of dollars per year [3]. Soiling refers to the accumulation of particulate and organic matter on the exposed surfaces of PV modules [4]. This leads to a reduction in solar irradiance transmittance and, consequently, power output losses [5]. This complex, highly site-specific phenomenon depends on local environmental conditions and module design, as well as the composition, deposition rate, and adhesion strength of soiling layers [6, 7]. Soiling deposits are usually a mixture of mineral dust, salts, atmospheric aerosols, organic residues and biological material from natural, urban or industrial sources [8, 9]. The impact of soiling on PV performance is influenced by its distribution, the amount and physicochemical properties of deposited material, as well as its adhesion behaviors [10, 11].

On the one hand, while uniform soiling causes a general reduction in power output, non-uniform or localized soiling poses a greater risk to system reliability by inducing partial shading and triggering hot spot formation. Studies have shown that localized deposits, such as bird droppings, can block sunlight on specific cells, leading to thermal stress and hot spots [12, 13]. Horizontal module configurations have also been associated with a higher risk of uneven soiling [13]. Since hot spots can result in module failures, their prevention is crucial for the safe operation of PV systems [14].

On the other hand, fine mineral dust can form optically dense layers that scatter and absorb light, while hygroscopic particles may promote cementation processes under humid conditions, increasing adhesion and complicating cleaning operations [15, 16]. Electrostatic interactions, surface roughness and local wind regimes can also affect deposition dynamics and natural cleaning events, resulting in significant spatial and temporal variability in soiling rates [6, 17, 18].

Desert regions are particularly vulnerable to soiling due to high dust concentrations, scarce precipitation and intense solar irradiance [6, 19–21]. These factors contribute to sustained and continuous deposition of materials, while simultaneously inhibiting the efficiency of natural removal processes. As a result, they create conditions that favor long-term accumulation and the persistence of soiling layers within the system. This vulnerability has driven research to focus primarily on the inorganic constituents of soiling, providing valuable insights into optical losses and cleaning strategies.

Numerous techniques have been developed to measure the impact of soiling on PV performance, including methods based on short-circuit current and I - V curve comparisons between clean and soiled modules [21–26], optical transmittance loss through reference sensors [27–30], or indirect estimation using software tools and environmental data [31–35]. These approaches provide key metrics such as the soiling ratio, either in field conditions or under controlled environments using solar simulators. Some methods rely on specialized hardware (e.g., Atonometrics MARS, Fracsun ARES, or the Kipp&Zonen DustIQ), while others use existing plant equipment or advanced algorithms to infer soiling losses. However, despite their relevance for energy performance

analysis, these methods do not address the role of microbiota in the adhesion, consolidation, and optical impact of soiling layers.

The potential role of biological components, especially microorganisms capable of forming biofilms and enhancing particle adhesion, has received limited attention [36, 37]. Understanding these interactions is essential for developing effective, site-specific mitigation strategies, particularly in regions with high solar potential where energy losses induced by soiling are economically significant [38]. This biological dimension remains largely unexplored in conventional soiling measurement approaches, yet it is particularly relevant in regions with high solar potential. Microorganisms are an essential component of all ecosystems, both natural and artificial. This includes environments subjected to extreme conditions, such as deserts. Their remarkable physiological plasticity enables them to colonize a wide variety of surfaces, ranging from soils to synthetic materials found in urban and industrial environments [38]. In these settings, microbial communities actively interact with their environment by producing extracellular compounds, forming biofilms and modifying the physicochemical properties of the surfaces they inhabit. These processes can alter surface stability, texture and particle retention capacity [37]. Under arid conditions, this microbial activity can promote the adhesion and consolidation of particulate matter to PV modules, contributing to crust formation and affecting system performance [38]. This biological perspective is particularly relevant in regions with high solar potential.

Despite the extensive research devoted to mineral dust and its optical and mechanical effects on PV performance, the biological dimension of soiling remains largely unexplored. The vast majority of studies address soiling as a purely physicochemical process, overlooking the potential contribution of microorganisms that colonize deposited particles and module surfaces. In addition, microbial colonization can significantly modify the adhesion, cohesion and stability of soiling layers through biofilm formation and the secretion of extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) (Insert EPS Reference). Many of the undesirable causes or reasons for efficiency loss in PV systems have not been fully explained solely by the behavior of inorganic dust. This is because these biological processes can promote crust consolidation, enhance dust retention, and alter cleaning efficiency. Therefore, investigating microbial soiling represents a novel and necessary step to move beyond mineral-centered approaches and achieve a holistic understanding of PV surface fouling, particularly in hyper-arid regions such as the Atacama Desert.

In this context, the present study aims to characterize the contribution of microbial communities to the soiling process of PV modules installed in the Atacama desert, which is one of the regions with the highest solar irradiance worldwide. The study evaluates biofilm formation on deposited particulate matter, its role in consolidating adhered crusts and its impact on the optical performance of PV modules. Integrating microbiological and morphological, the research elucidates the interactions between microbiota and soiling, providing evidence to inform the development of mitigation strategies that account for microbial contributions.

FIGURE 1 | A) Map showing the location of the ‘soiling’ sampling sites in the Atacama Desert and their Köppen climate classification [39]. B) A satellite image of the Atacama Desert, obtained from the NASA Worldview application (<https://worldview.earthdata.nasa.gov>; accessed 22 May 2025), showing its location within the NASA Earth Science Data and Information System (ESDIS). C) Schematic representation of the altitudinal profile where the sampling points are located. D) PV modules sampled at UA. E) PV modules sampled at PSDA.

2 | Methodology

2.1 | Study Area

The study was conducted at two representative sites in the Atacama desert in northern Chile: The Coloso campus of University of Antofagasta (UA) in the coastal city of Antofagasta (23.70°S, 70.42°W) and the Plataforma Solar del Desierto de Atacama (PSDA) (24.09°S, 69.93°W) (see Figure 1A–C). Antofagasta is located at sea level and has a warm desert climate (BWh), influenced by maritime conditions. In contrast, PSDA is situated at an elevation of approximately 1000 m in a continental desert environment, with a cold desert climate (BWk) according to the Köppen–Geiger classification (Figure 1A). This geographical distribution enables the comparison of two contrasting scenarios within the same desert: one under coastal and urban influence and the other representative of the desert interior, with extreme radiation and aridity.

Soiling sampling was carried out on uncleaned PV modules with two years’ exposure in Antofagasta and one year’s exposure in PSDA (see Figure 1D,E). Samples were collected using sterile, fine-bristle brushes, applied vertically over six modules per site. The collected material was homogenized to obtain a composite

sample of approximately 35 g per site, which was then stored under sterile conditions until laboratory analysis.

2.2 | Microbiological Characterization and Molecular Analysis

To characterize the cultivable microbiota, three different culture media with different nutrient levels were used: Luria-Bertani (LB) for fast-growing bacteria; Reasoner’s 2A (R2A) for oligotrophic microorganisms; and a low phosphate mineral salts as a minimum medium, which is recommended for bacteria associated with inorganic surfaces. Particles were suspended in 10 mL of sterile saline solution (0.85% NaCl) from 1 g of soil sample (UA and PSDA), shaken for 2 h at 37°C, and serially diluted (10^{-1} – 10^{-6}). Each dilution was then inoculated onto solid media supplemented with cycloheximide and incubated at 30°C for 96 h. Colonies were selected based on their morphology, pigmentation and edge characteristics. They were then cultivated in LB medium and preserved in 25% glycerol at –80°C. A total of 34 bacterial strains was isolated (25 from UA and 9 from PSDA).

To evaluate the capacity for colonization, biofilms were developed in a Class II biosafety cabinet (Biobase) under sterile conditions.

Soil from each site (1 g) was suspended in 9 mL of 10% LB medium. This was then shaken at 230 rpm and 37°C for 1 h. Next, 500 μ L of the supernatant was inoculated into 250 mL Erlenmeyer flasks containing 50 mL of the same medium and a sterile PV glass substrate (2 cm \times 2 cm). Uninoculated controls were included to rule out environmental contamination. The experimental design consisted of 18 flasks: Twelve were dedicated to PV performance evaluation (I - V curves), with incubation periods of 2 and 7 d (three replicates per condition), and six were used for morphological analysis by FE-SEM Sigma 360. For FE-SEM imaging, samples were sputter-coated with gold. The flasks were then incubated in a temperature-controlled shaking bath (WSB-45, WITEG Labortechnik) at 37°C and 150 rpm. The biomass adhering to the substrates was determined using a gravimetric method: the substrates were weighed before and after incubation to calculate the mass difference (mg/cm^2).

DNA from cultivable isolates was extracted using the DNeasy UltraClean Microbial kit (Qiagen, USA). Biofilm DNA was extracted using the DNeasy PowerSoil kit (Qiagen, USA) from substrates incubated for 7 d (6–8 per site). DNA concentration was measured with a Qubit 4 fluorometer (Invitrogen), and integrity was evaluated by 0.8% agarose gel electrophoresis. Amplification of the 16S rRNA gene was performed using primers 27F/1492R and the 16S Barcoding Kit (Oxford Nanopore Technologies) with the following program: 95°C for 1 min; 25 cycles of 95°C for 20 s, 55°C for 30 s, and 65°C for 2 min; and a final extension at 65°C for 5 min. Sequencing was carried out on a GridION Mk system (Oxford Nanopore Technologies) using FLO-MIN106 (R9.4) flow cells for 6 h. Reads were filtered using a quality threshold of $Q \geq 7$, and adapters were removed with Porechop. Taxonomic analysis was performed using EMU (v5.6), applying an abundance threshold of 0.01 and discarding taxa below this value. The resulting OTU tables were analyzed using the Microbiome Analyst platform [40].

2.3 | Influence of Biofilms on the Electrical Performance of Photovoltaic Module

Two strains of the genus *Dietzia* (*D. maris* and *D. kunjamenis* subsp. *schimae*), which were previously isolated from UA and PSDA, respectively, were selected due to their high relative abundance in cultivable isolates. Both strains were recovered from cryopreservation and cultivated in a liquid LB medium until they reached an optical density of 1 at 600 nm. The cultures were then centrifuged, and the resulting cell pellets were subjected to carotenoid extraction via bead-beating with zirconium beads in methanol. The resulting organic fraction was stored in the dark under refrigeration until analysis.

Carotenoids characterization was performed using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) on a Jasco LC-4000 system (Tokyo, Japan), which was equipped with a PU-2089S Plus quaternary pump and an MD-4010 diode array detector. The system was controlled using ChromNAV Control Center V.2 software. A reverse-phase column C-18 LiChrospher RP-149 18 (5 μ m) (4.6 \times 150 mm) was used. The mobile phase consisted of a solvent mixture of water and methanol (2:8, v/v) for solvent A and a solvent mixture of acetone and methanol (1:1, v/v) for solvent B.

For carotenoid identification, retention time and visible spectral profile with those of an analytical lutein standard (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA). Additionally, the spectral characteristics were compared with those obtained from standard PV glass to exclude potential interference.

The impact of biofilms on PV performance was evaluated using current-voltage (I - V) curves obtained on PV glass substrates containing biofilms cultured from UA and PSDA for 2 and 7 d, using clean PV glass substrates as controls. I - V measurements were performed at room temperature using a CT80AAA solar simulator (Photo Emission Tech) equipped with a 300 W xenon (Xe) arc lamp to reproduce the AM 1.5 G solar spectrum at an intensity of 100 mW/cm^2 (1 sun). The system was calibrated using a PET-certified crystalline silicon (c-Si) reference cell (model #60909), and the I - V curves were recorded with a Keithley 2400 Source Meter. Each experimental condition was evaluated in triplicate, and average values were used to ensure statistical representativeness.

3 | Results and Discussion

3.1 | Taxonomic Composition and Diversity of Cultivable and Biofilm-Forming Microbial Communities

A total of 34 bacterial isolates exhibiting a wide phenotypic diversity were obtained from the soiling material collected from PV modules at UA and PSDA. These isolates primarily displayed yellow, orange, and pink pigmentation. The highest diversity was observed on LB agar medium, yielding 25 isolates from UA and nine from PSDA. Phylogenetic analysis based on 16S rRNA gene sequencing (Nanopore) revealed that these isolates corresponded to seven different species (see Table 1). Samples from UA included the genera *Arthrobacter*, *Kocuria*, and *Dietzia*, whereas PSDA samples were dominated by *Arthrobacter* and *Dietzia*. At species level, UA samples comprised *A. tecti*, *A. subterraneus*, *A. tumbae*, *A. parietis*, *K. turfanensis*, *D. kunjamenis* subsp. *schimae* and *D. maris*, while PSDA samples included *A. subterraneus*, *A. parietis*, *D. kunjamenis* subsp. *schimae* and *D. maris*.

The bacterial isolates obtained from soiling on PV modules at UA and PSDA revealed a community dominated by three genera of the phylum Actinobacteria: *Arthrobacter*, *Kocuria*, and *Dietzia*. The *Arthrobacter* species identified (*A. tecti*, *A. subterraneus*, *A. tumbae*, and *A. parietis*) are consistent with previous studies reporting this genus on rock surfaces, ancient building materials, and arid environments [39, 41]. Notably, *A. parietis* and *A. tumbae* have been isolated from walls and Egyptian tombs, highlighting their preference for inert, dry substrates with intermittent solar exposure [42]. *A. subterraneus*, detected at both sampling sites, has been described as an oligotrophic microorganism with high tolerance to low humidity, limited nutrient availability, and energy scarcity [43]. These traits support the role of *Arthrobacter* species in colonizing artificial substrates in extreme desert environments, aided by their capacity to synthesize carotenoid pigments and antioxidant enzymes that provide protection against solar irradiation and oxidative stress [44].

TABLE 1 | Cultivable bacterial species identified from soiling deposited on PV modules at UA and PSDA.

Genus	Species	Site	Culture medium	Accession number
<i>Arthrobacter</i>	<i>Arthrobacter tecti</i>	UA	LB-agar	NR_042251
<i>Arthrobacter</i>	<i>Arthrobacter subterraneus</i>	UA, PSDA	LB-agar	OK135682
<i>Arthrobacter</i>	<i>Arthrobacter tumbae</i>	UA	LB-agar	KJ575034
<i>Arthrobacter</i>	<i>Arthrobacter parietis</i>	UA, PSDA	LB-agar	MN204053
<i>Kocuria</i>	<i>Kocuria turfanensis</i>	UA	LB-agar	CP014480
<i>Dietzia</i>	<i>Dietzia kunjamenis subsp. schimae</i>	UA, PSDA	LB-agar	CP143297.1
<i>Dietzia</i>	<i>Dietzia maris</i>	UA, PSDA	LB-agar	CP099712.1

For the genus *Kocuria*, the isolated species (*K. turfanensis*), originally described from the Turpan Desert, one of the hottest and driest deserts in the world [45], exhibited traits consistent with its occurrence under Atacama desert conditions. Previous research from arid zones has highlighted *Kocuria's* resistance to ultraviolet (UV) radiation, desiccation, and temperature fluctuations, characteristics also observed in isolates from high-altitude and saline environments [46, 47]. Regarding *Dietzia*, two species were identified, *D. kunjamenis subsp. schimae* and *D. maris*, in both sampling locations. In contrast to reports from less extreme climates in Europe and North America, where this genus has not been detected [48], its presence in the Atacama Desert suggests a strong adaptive capacity. *D. kunjamenis*, originally isolated from the Himalayas, a high-altitude environment with intense UV radiation and low temperatures, demonstrates remarkable ecological plasticity, whereas *D. maris*, commonly associated with marine and coastal habitats, is known for producing antioxidant compounds and photoprotective pigments such as melanin [49]. The detection of these two *Dietzia* species on artificial surfaces exposed to hyper-arid conditions and intense solar radiation underscores the genus' high tolerance and versatility in extreme environments.

The metagenomic analysis of biofilms deposited on PV module surfaces revealed marked differences in microbial community composition between the two study sites (Figure 2). In the urban area of Antofagasta, the community was dominated by Gram-positive genera known for their biofilm-forming capacity and resilience under extreme conditions, including *Bacillus* (*B. tianshenii*, *B. freudenreichii*, *B. horti*, *B. dafuensis*, *B. infantis*, *B. songklensis*), *Sporosarcina* (*S. koreensis*, *S. soli*, *S. luteola*, *S. saromensis*), *Bhargavaea* (*B. beijingensis*, *B. cecembensis*), *Mesobacillus* (*M. subterraneus*, *M. maritimus*, *M. litoralis*, *M. persicus*), *Cytobacillus* (*C. oceanisediminis*, *C. ciccensis*, *C. eiseniae*), *Caldakalibacillus* (*C. mannanilyticus*), and *Planococcus* (*P. dechangensis*, *P. plakortidis*, *P. glaciei*). These genera have been widely reported for their tolerance to high UV radiation, desiccation, and nutrient scarcity, conditions commonly found on PV module surfaces in arid regions [50]. In contrast, the PSDA site, located in a continental desert environment, exhibited a simpler community dominated by *Peribacillus* (*P. frigoritolerans*, *P. muralis*, *P. simplex*) and *Kocuria* (*K. rizophila*), both previously

reported as efficient biofilm formers under oligotrophic and stress-prone conditions [51]. The prevalence of *Kocuria* in PSDA biofilms is consistent with its previously described resistance to UV radiation, extreme temperature fluctuations, and desiccation stress, traits that facilitate survival on artificial surfaces exposed to harsh environmental conditions.

Community diversity indices further emphasized these differences: UA biofilms exhibited higher species richness (Alpha-Chao1) and diversity (Alpha-Shannon) compared to PSDA biofilms (Figure 3). Similar reductions in alpha diversity have been reported in early-stage biofilm formation, where surface colonization triggers interspecific competition and physiological specialization among the microbial community [52]. The lower alpha diversity observed in PSDA biofilms is comparable to values reported for microbial communities in cold desert soils, where abiotic stressors such as temperature and water availability impose strong selective pressure [21].

These results indicate that not all bacterial taxa present in the initial soiling were able to transition into stable biofilm communities. Instead, PV module surfaces appear to act as a selective filter, favoring microorganisms capable of strong adhesion, metabolic efficiency under nutrient limitation, and tolerance to high UV radiation. This ecological filtering likely contributes to the establishment of stress-tolerant genera such as *Kocuria* and *Peribacillus* in PSDA and the more diverse community observed in UA, where environmental conditions are comparatively milder and influenced by urban factors.

To complement the metagenomic characterization, controlled incubation assays of particulate material on PV glass surfaces were conducted to evaluate the potential of microbial communities to form biofilms. FE-SEM was employed for this purpose, as it enables high-resolution observation of bacterial adhesion, cell morphology and spatial organization at different stages of development. The FE-SEM images showed the progressive development of bacterial biofilms on PV glass surfaces using particulate material collected from UA (Figure 4A–C) and PSDA (Figure 4D–F). After two days of incubation, coccoid and coccobacillary cells were observed either individually or

FIGURE 2 | Characterization of the microbial community forming biofilms at UA and PSDA using hierarchical clustering at the species level based on the UPGMA (unweighted pair group method with arithmetic mean) method.

FIGURE 3 | Diversity analysis of microbial communities forming biofilms at UA and PSDA. A) Alpha diversity index—Chao1. B) Alpha diversity index—Shannon.

in small aggregates ranging in size from 0.5 to 1.5 μm . These structures represent an early stage of biofilm formation, during which the bacteria begin to adhere actively to the substrate and establish initial microcolonies. The observed morphologies are consistent with the genera which were identified in this study and have been described in previous reports as adhering to and persisting on artificial surfaces under extreme environmental conditions [53].

After five days of incubation (see Figure 4B,E), a more advanced stage of community organization began to emerge, characterized by the formation of a polymeric extracellular matrix that connected multiple cells. This matrix is visible as a 3D network enveloping bacterial microaggregates and facilitates the formation of a cohesive structure that supports water retention, UV protection and overall biofilm consolidation. Specific areas in the micrographs highlight regions where the matrix begins to surround the cells, thereby promoting aggregation and enhancing their survival under environmental stress. By day 7 (see Figure 4C,F), the biofilm had almost completely covered the glass surface. The UA biofilm (Figure 4C) appeared dense and homogeneous, whereas the PSDA biofilm (Figure 4F) showed a more heterogeneous and less compact structure. These differences suggest a higher colonization capacity in UA, which is potentially linked to the greater microbial diversity and richness revealed by the metagenomic analysis.

In addition to its structural function, the observed extracellular matrix also plays an active role in cementing particulate matter. As can be seen in micrographs B and E, this network allows mineral particles to be retained and incorporated into the biofilm, forming compact layers with high mechanical stability. This process has previously been reported in arid soils and on artificial surfaces and represents a key mechanism that contributes to the persistence of soiling and reduces the effectiveness of conventional cleaning methods [54]. In the context of the Atacama Desert, which is characterized by intense UV radiation, low humidity and continuous mineral deposition, these findings highlight the essential role of microbial communities in forming cemented crusts on PV modules.

3.2 | Microbial Pigments in Soiling Communities: Spectral Characterization and Potential Implications for PV Performance

The HPLC analysis of bacterial extracts from *Dietzia maris* (UA) and *Dietzia kunjamensis subsp. schimae* (PSDA) revealed the presence of a carotenoid pigment with a specific retention time and an absorption spectrum in the visible region with spectral features consistent with photoprotective xanthophylls [50, 51, 55] (see Figure 5A–D). The respective retention times were 14.107, 14.577, 20.820 and 23.407 for *D. maris* and 14.577, 17.923, and 21.577 for *D. kunjamensis subsp. schimae*. These two strains were selected due to their relative abundance and successful isolation; the analysis focused on the strain most representative of the *Dietzia* genus. In consideration of the limitations that an HPLC-DAD analysis may have compared to LC-MS, we obtained a robust tentative classification and identification of carotenoids based on the match between the retention time of the authentic lutein pigment standard and the characteristic visible absorption spectra of the detected pigments. For the objectives of this study, which focused on assessing the presence and photoprotective role of microbial pigments, this level of characterization was considered sufficient.

The visible spectra of the extracted compounds showed intense absorption in the 400–500 nm range, with maxima between 445 and 450 nm, a pattern typical of carotenoids found in photosynthetic microorganisms and organisms adapted to high-radiation environments [50, 51, 55, 56]. In particular, one of the carotenoid peaks showed a retention time and spectral pattern consistent with lutein, allowing a preliminary classification of the primary pigment as lutein-like or as a closely related structural analogue, while additional peaks with absorption features characteristic of xanthophyll-type carotenoids were also detected. To our knowledge, this is the first evidence of such pigments in *Dietzia* strains associated with microbial communities forming the soiling layer on PV modules in the Atacama Desert. While previous studies have reported *D. maris* primarily as a producer of canthaxanthin, another carotenoid of industrial interest [54], our findings expand the known diversity of carotenoids in this genus. The presence of these pigments suggests an adaptive mechanism by which these

FIGURE 4 | A–C) FE-SEM images of biofilm-forming microbiota on PV glass surfaces from soiling samples collected at U. D–F) Biofilm-associated microbiota on PV glass from soiling deposited at PSDA.

bacteria can withstand extreme conditions, such as high levels of UV radiation and oxidative stress. They may also influence the interaction between the biofilm and the PV glass surface. It is hypothesized that these biomolecules provide protection for microbial communities and may also contribute to the attenuation of incident light, thereby interfering with the system’s optical efficiency. Indeed, significant overlap was observed between the

absorption spectrum of the detected pigment and the spectral range of maximum PV conversion efficiency in monocrystalline silicon PV modules (400–700 nm) [57]. This overlap could lead to competitive photon absorption, thereby reducing the amount of usable energy available for electricity generation. Schmidt et al. [58] have previously reported this phenomenon, demonstrating that the accumulation of microbial chromophores on PV surfaces

FIGURE 5 | HPLC chromatograms and Visible absorption spectra of carotenoid extracts from *Dietzia* strains. A,B) *D. maris* (UA). C,D) *D. kunjamensis* subsp. *schimae* (PSDA). B,D) Visible absorption spectra and retention times of a lutein-type carotenoid or a closely related structural analogue (1) and (2, 3, 4) characteristic patterns of carotenoids. Absorption maxima and retention times were obtained using a diode-array detector.

can induce performance losses associated with unwanted optical mechanisms.

It is worth noting that the production of carotenoid pigments in *Dietzia* species is not exclusive to the Atacama Desert. Previous studies have documented their presence in a variety of extreme

environments around the world, including the Indian Himalayas, where *D. kunjamensis* was originally isolated, as well as in marine habitats deep beneath the ocean's surface, in hypersaline lakes in Africa, and in hydrothermal fields in the southwestern Indian Ocean [21, 59]. These bacteria's ability to synthesize antioxidant and photoprotective compounds has also been exploited in

FIGURE 6 | The I - V curves were obtained using a solar simulator on PV glass substrates and minimodules with biofilms cultivated from microbial strains isolated at UA (A) and PSDA (B), respectively.

industrial bioprocesses, particularly in canthaxanthin production by *D. natronolimnaea* [60, 61]. From this perspective, the discovery of pigmented *Dietzia* strains on PV surfaces provides ecological evidence of microbial adaptation mechanisms to soiling in arid zones and opens up new opportunities for biotechnological applications. These microorganisms could be used as a natural source of functional compounds for protective coatings, for example, or for self-cleaning technologies and bioactive formulations designed to mitigate the impact of soiling and improve the performance of PV systems in environments with high solar radiation.

Following the detection of carotenoid compounds in *Dietzia* strains, the effect of biofilm formation on the electrical performance of PV minimodules was examined. Laboratory I - V curve measurements revealed significant I_{sc} losses after seven days of microbial colonization compared to 2 d, directly correlated with an increase in surface biomass accumulation. In UA samples, I_{sc} losses ranged from 15.20% to 30.66% (19.5 mA), whereas in PSDA samples losses fluctuated between 11.01% and 20.12% (12.8 mA). Surface biomass increased from 0.054 to 0.167 mg cm⁻² in UA and from 0.021 to 0.056 mg cm⁻² in PSDA between days 2 and 7 of colonization (Figure 6A,B). These findings demonstrate that even modest increases in microbial biomass can induce substantial electrical losses on PV surfaces. These results are comparable to values reported in the literature, where typical daily and monthly soiling losses in PV systems under arid and semi-arid conditions range from 0.2 % to 0.7 %, and can reach up to 1% per day, and from 2 % to over 10 % per month, with higher losses observed during dry seasons or extreme dust events [62–66]. For example, in Kuwait, soiling losses reached 45.8% over a 3-month period without cleaning, while some studies show losses of 33.5% in one month in Saudi Arabia [67].

Such behavior is consistent with previous reports describing the biofilm-forming ability of UV-tolerant strains under conditions of extreme solar radiation like the Atacama desert [49]. While

our experiments were carried out under controlled laboratory conditions, they confirm that biofilm growth represents a relevant mechanism of performance loss in PV modules, particularly in regions exposed to intense solar irradiation.

The results obtained show that the presence of microbiota on PV surfaces contributes to the observed optical and electrical losses and also modifies the adhesion and consolidation properties of the deposit. The formation of extracellular polymeric matrices, as evidenced by FE-SEM analysis, explains the high cohesion of the adhered material and reduced cleaning efficiency. This establishes a direct link between microbial activity, surface cementation, and performance losses as evidenced in the I - V curves. Conventional cleaning procedures therefore struggle to remove deposits in which the biopolymeric matrix confers high cohesion and resistance to detachment.

Conventional cleaning methods, such as dry brushing and rinsing with water, have been shown to be only partially effective against microbial contamination [68, 69]. This resistance is associated with the presence of a protective matrix composed of EPS, which includes polysaccharides, proteins, nucleic acids, and lipids. These substances provide mechanical stability and promote cell adhesion to glass. While dry brushing can remove loose mineral particles, it cannot disrupt the cohesive biofilm network that anchors microbial cells. Its hydrophobic nature also restricts the effectiveness of mechanical agents [68]. Similarly, rinsing with demineralized water alone does not achieve complete removal, as treated surfaces maintain a persistent microbial load [69].

Overall, the results suggest that the microorganisms present in the soiling layers are active agents that promote the consolidation of the deposit and reduce optical transmittance, rather than passive components. This shows that the biological component plays a relevant role even in extremely arid environments such as the Atacama Desert and should be considered when formulating soiling models and designing cleaning strategies for PV systems.

4 | Conclusions

This study provides novel insights into the biological mechanisms underlying the formation and consolidation of soiling layers on PV surfaces in arid environments. Microbial communities isolated from PV modules in the Atacama Desert, as well as those forming biofilms, demonstrated a high adaptive capacity adaptive that favors their persistence under extreme desiccation and solar exposure. A key finding was the production of extracellular polymeric substances that promote particle retention and crust formation, as confirmed by FE-SEM images showing dense 3D matrices encapsulating cells and mineral particles.

Chromatographic analyses revealed the synthesis of lutein-like carotenoids in *Dietzia maris* and *D. kunjamensis subsp. schimae*, pigments that not only enhance microbial survival but also overlap with the spectral range of PV energy conversion, thus creating a mechanism of optical interference.

It is important to note that the biofilm formation experiments were designed as short-term or accelerated assays intended to reproduce, within a manageable laboratory timeframe, the early stages of microbial adhesion and biofilm consolidation that would normally develop over longer periods under natural desert exposure. Under these controlled conditions, the availability of nutrients and stable temperature favored rapid biofilm development, leading to current losses that represent an upper boundary of the potential impact. In real field environments, microbial colonization would occur more gradually and be influenced by fluctuating environmental factors such as irradiance, humidity, dust availability, and nutrient input. Although the biofilms were directly associated with short-circuit current losses of up to 30.66% in UA and 20.12% in PSDA samples under laboratory conditions, values that may not directly reflect typical field magnitudes. Nevertheless, they demonstrate that even moderate biofilm formation can produce measurable optical attenuation and electrical performance losses. This supports the interpretation that microbial activity, though often overlooked, can substantially contribute to long-term soiling behavior in PV systems operating under desert conditions, underscoring its significant impact on performance even under controlled laboratory conditions.

Overall, our findings demonstrate that intense solar radiation does not inhibit microbial colonization but instead selects for resilient taxa capable of forming persistent soiling layers. Microorganisms thus emerge not as passive contaminants but as active agents shaping the long-term behavior of PV systems in desert regions. Recognizing their role is essential for developing predictive soiling models and site-specific mitigation strategies. Future research should focus on biofilm-resistant coatings, microbial-inhibiting surface treatments, and biotechnological approaches that integrate these insights into practical solutions for large-scale solar deployment.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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